

formed the main plot and seed rates the subplot. Seeds of FARO 11 were drilled along furrows made 25 cm apart or dibbled 25 cm within and between rows.

For initial weed control, a combination of thiobencarb + propanil at 3 kg ai/ha was applied to all treatments 7 d after sowing. Weed weight and grain yield were determined at maturity and grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Seed rate and crop establishment

techniques did not significantly reduce weed weight; however, weed weight declined progressively as seed rate increased.

Highest yield was with 45 kg seeds/ha (Table 1), probably because of less competition among rice plants than at higher rates. Crop establishment techniques did not significantly affect grain yield (Table 2); however, dibbling gave the highest yield. *ℳ*

Table 2. Effect of crop establishment techniques on weed growth and yield of FARO 11, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Establishment method	Dry weed weight (g/m ²)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Drilling	0.43	0.8
Dibbling	0.63	1.0
Broadcasting	0.19	0.7
LSD	0.05	0.4

^a Drought at flowering stage caused generally poor grain yield.

Response of lowland rice to phosphorus fertilizer

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Next to N, P is the second major nutrient element that limits rice yield. Response to P varies with soil characteristics. In Punjab, the rice area has expanded to include light-textured soils that often are P deficient. We studied the response of rice to P in farmer fields at five sites around the State. Soil characteristics of the fields are given in Table 1. N at 120 kg/ha was applied to all fields in 3 equal splits. Different levels of P and 12.5 kg K/ha were incorporated during the last puddling, and 35-d-old PR106 seedlings were transplanted.

Applying 13.5 kg P/ha increased rice

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of soils at five sites in the Punjab.

Classification	Texture	pH	Organic C (%)	EC (mmho/cm)	Available P (kg/ha)
Haplustalf	Sandy loam	8.4	0.54	0.35	5.6
Ustochrept	Sandy loam	8.4	0.65	0.38	38.8
Haplustalf	Sandy loam	8.3	0.51	0.40	11.6
Ustochrept	Sandy loam	9.0	0.40	0.24	1.8
Ustochrept	Clay loam	8.5	0.41	0.35	12.1

yield by 300 to 740 kg/ha at 3 sites, but the differences were not significant. At 2 sites, there was a significant response to 19.5 kg P/ha. Mean values for all sites showed that applying 19.5 kg P/ha increase rice yield by 330 kg (Table 2). Rice did not respond to 26 kg P/ha.

Although the response to fertilizer P was not substantial, the results indicate that P application is necessary to achieve optimum rice yield in Punjab. Because rice - wheat is a common rotation, P not utilized by the rice crop

Table 2. Response of rice to fertilizer P at 5 sites in the Punjab.

P (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)					
	1	2	3	4	5	Mean
0	8.0	8.5	6.9	6.8	1.2	7.5
13.5	8.4	9.3	6.8	1.0	1.5	1.8
19.5	1.9	9.2	1.6	1.2	1.5	1.8
26.0	8.5	9.0	1.5	1.2	1.1	7.9
CD at 5%	ns	ns	0.5	0.2	ns	

is utilized by the succeeding wheat crop. *ℳ*

Effect of split-applied N on rice yields

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We evaluated the effect of split application of N fertilizer on rice yield at TNRRI. Nine N application times were tested with ADT36 (105-110 d variety) in 1984 wet season (Jun-Sep) in a randomized block design. Soil was clay loam with 0.13% N, 1.2% organic matter, and cation exchange capacity 23 ml/litre.

Prilled urea (at 75 kg N/ha) was applied in 2 or 3 splits at planting, 5 d after transplanting (DT), 10 DT, and 15 DT with 50 + 25 + 25% splits or 4 equal splits. This was compared with 0 fertilizer N and all basal N. PK at 38 kg was applied to all plots.

Grain yield was maximum (5.4 t/ha) with 3 splits (see table), and was significantly superior to that of both checks.

Basal 25% N appeared adequate if applied before 10 DT followed by splits. Basal 50% N was also adequate if applied after 10 DT and followed by splits. *ℳ*

Effect of split application of 75 kg N/ha on grain yield of a short-duration rice variety, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
0 N (check)	3.6 h
All N at planting (check)	4.4 g
50% at planting + 2 equal splits	4.9 ef
25% at planting + 2 equal splits	5.1 bcd
50% at 5 DT + 2 equal splits	5.2 abcd
25% at 5 DT + 3 equal splits	5.3 ab
50% at 10 DT + 2 equal splits	5.4 a
25% at 10 DT + 3 equal splits	5.0 def
50% at 15 DT + 2 equal splits	5.0 def
25% at 15 DT + 3 equal splits	4.8 f

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.